

The Role of Policy in City-Region Food System Transformation: Evidence from Living Labs across the EU

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Abstract

The rising need for system wide food system transformation is recognised across the nexus of environmental sustainability, human health, social justice, and economics. As scholars and practitioners focus their efforts on the complexity and pressures of food systems, Living Labs are conceptualised as experimentation grounds for city region food system (CRFS) transformation, engaging with the urban-rural continuum of food. Yet, the role that local policy can play in the transformation process is unknown. This paper presents an assessment of CRFS labs across the EU, focusing on food stakeholders and policy actor perspectives to provide insight into policy initiatives, policy instruments and the factors influencing food transformation policies at city-region level. In-depth semi-structured interviews with CRFS lab coordinators from thirteen EU city-regions capture the variation in characteristics of CRFS. Lessons are drawn on policy efforts and experimentation, which portrays the diversity of approaches and the power dynamics, local capacities, mandates, and priorities in urban (food) agendas. Mapping out responses to CRFS challenges demonstrates a transition from top-down to citizen-driven collaborative models where citizens, local governments and organisations play an increasing role in the development and implementation of transformative activities and policies. Findings also stress current gaps in cross-scale governance collaboration and highlight the need for adopting system thinking principles in the urban food governance discourse, moving away from monomeric responses to the calls for sustainability in CRFS.

Key words

Living Lab, Policy Lab, Food Governance, Food System Transformation, City Region Food System (CRFS), Sustainability

Introduction

The need for food system transformation to increase environmental sustainability and human health is increasingly recognised and permeates governance and policy strategies at the international, European, and national levels. Despite the recognition that these issues negatively impact society, food systems governance has been limited. The current tools and strategies used to steer food systems towards sustainability have been criticised due to their fragmentation and oversimplification (Ballamingie et al., 2020; Blay-Palmer et al., 2015; Moragues-Faus & Sonnino, 2019; Sibbing et al., 2021; Sonnino et al., 2019). Particularly the lack of systems thinking in EU's food governance has led to a fragmented and disconnected approach and a concentration of power in the hands of market actors (SAPEA, 2020).

City regions are emerging as a new nexus for urban transformations surrounding policy, research, and food innovation. The City Region Food System (CRFS) approach is based on the concentration of flows of resources and impacts within the high demand city region food systems, and therefore focuses on the city region as an appropriate and effective locus of policy and transformation activities (Blay-Palmer et al., 2018). The momentum in city-regions is demonstrated by the uptake of food into strategies and development plans that policymakers undertake (Dubbeling et al., 2015; Jennings, 2015), as well as participation in city networks, bottom-up urban initiatives, and local governments' declarations (e.g., the MUFPP (Milan Urban Food Policy Pact)) towards establishing more sustainable, fair, and resilient urban processes that frame urban agendas accordingly.

However, city-regions remain challenged by the growing pool and variation of food actors and the collective interest involved with food system transformation. Living Labs have sprung up in multiple development areas, including the agri-food economy, and grassroots innovation in the wider food system (Wolfert et al., 2010; Campbell Angus Donald, 2017). The Living Labs approach plays a vital role in transformational processes as its core concepts evolves around open innovation, based upon the processes of prototyping, validation, and continuous development of solutions in dynamic and complex solutions. This facilitates policy experimentation, co-creation, and citizen involvement within the evolving real life policy contexts in which city-region food system transformation takes place.

Embedded in this emerging stream of interdisciplinary practice, there is an on-going academic debate on the role of cities in sustainable food transitions. Scholars from many

disciplines have widely discussed the need for a system thinking approach to food, and the role of policymaking and urban experimentation in addressing complex sustainability issues in urban territories (Blay-Palmer et al., 2018; Moragues-Faus et al., 2017; Sonnino et al., 2019). But as many have argued, there is still a need for more empirical and place-specific research that focuses on practical elements (Candel, 2014; Sonnino, 2023; Wolfram et al., 2016), such as local government decision making (Candel, 2020), the role of system thinking in local governance (Sonnino et al., 2019), and the role that Living Labs play in the overall sustainable transition of food systems. At the same time, to date, according to (Frantzeskaki, 2019), “the majority of the cases are analysed and documented in time-distance to contemporary urban agendas and policy issues”. This research replies to these gaps and calls and assesses the application of the City Region Food System approach to develop viable and sustainable city-region policies and governance that entails the diversity and uniqueness of city-region food systems (Eakin et al., 2017). The focus of this paper is on the food system transformation efforts of city regions across the EU, joining the discourse on policy and governance to reach food system sustainability. Consequently, we question the types of policies and strategies that city-regions in the EU follow. How does the concept of Living Lab help them to experiment and co-design such policies in a bottom-up manner together with citizens? Ultimately, what’s their relationship with different levels and scales of food governance?

Urban food policy transformation: from theory to practice

Understanding the theoretical concepts of urban food system transformation is required to successfully coordinate transformation efforts and deal with socio-environmental challenges linked to food system sustainability. Complex problems with multi-causality and diverse interlinked interactions must be addressed if sustainable transformation in production, processing, transportation, consumption, and food waste is to be reached on a territorial scale (Ericksen, 2008). Multiple systemic concepts apply to this context. Academic discourse of the food system contains definitions and conceptualisations of the term sustainability. This research adopts the food system sustainability definition of the FAO (2018): “*a food system that delivers food security and nutrition for all in such a way that the economic, social and environmental bases to generate food security and nutrition for future generations are not compromised*”. This definition stresses the flexible and adaptive alignment of human and ecological needs across diverse scales (Eakin et al., 2017) to generate positive value cross the economic, social, and environmental aspects simultaneously.

Region-specific approach to food systems: the territorial dimension of food system transformation

Until recently, cities were seen as sole drivers of socio-environmental problems, operating under fragmented governance structures and limited agency. However, city planners, urban practitioners and policymakers have started to perceive cities as agents of action that can drive change, and as terrains of policy experimentation (Hebinck & Page, 2017; Wolfram et al., 2016). Even though urban transformations discourse has focused primarily on mega-cities (Hölscher et al., 2021), medium-sized and middle-income cities are increasingly acknowledged as leaders of sustainable transformation (Vojnovic, 2014), and are a good middle-ground for food policy experimentation (Ballamingie et al., 2020). Given the territorial proximity of food processes and actors, these cities and city-regions can opt for more integrated and sustainable food system processes that enable shorter food supply chains and connect farmers and consumers more directly, transforming the food system.

City-regions can enhance food security and urban resilience by adopting the City Region Food System (CRFS) approach. A CRFS is defined as *“the complex network of actors, processes and relationships to do with food production, processing, marketing, and consumption that exist in a given geographical region”* (Jennings, 2015, p.29). The city-region consists of several overlapping and interacting systems that have varying boundaries, with the territories of some systems spilling across city borders or across wider networks. The recognition of a lack of food system governance has led to a shift in focus towards city-regions as the nexus of food system transformation. The approach is characterised by diversity and involvement of institutional and societal partners in food governance. CRFS particularly focuses on the elements of (1) food access, (2) stimulating jobs and income, (3) resilience of the region and the food system, (4) improving the urban-rural linkage, (5) ecosystem and resource management and (6) participatory governance (Blay-Palmer et al., 2015, 2018). The region-specific concept of CRFS can stimulate sustainable operations by enabling democratic and bottom-up governance approaches in the local level and helps building more inclusive political narratives (Dubbeling et al., 2015; Moragues-Faus & Morgan, 2015). CRFS are considered a hub for innovation and new food governance that foster the creation of new relations between the state, the market and civil society (Wiskerke, 2009), functioning as a potential nexus to fill the vacuum left

by the lack of integrated and coherent food policies (Rocha, 2009; Sonnino, 2016; Moragues-Faus et al., 2017).

Typologies of food policy initiatives

The role of policy should be explored in food system transformation under the domain of city-region governance. Policymaking is a process of steering and orchestrating activities towards certain outcomes and is an essential part of governance. New configurations of food policies and different policy types form part of governance-beyond-the-state processes that allow policy experimentation over different scales of governance (Moragues-Faus & Morgan, 2015). The concept of *new food governance* is introduced by Renting & Wiskerke (2010) and describes a governance mode that goes beyond states' traditional roles, and entails the co-existence of civil society, the state, and the market. This governance thinking brings power and agency to non-traditional urban actors such as citizens and grassroots organisations and democratises urban processes and policymaking.

Policy typologies are helpful in assessing policy instruments and approaches. One such approach is the distinction between soft and hard policy instruments, given the level of coerciveness. A commonly used policy typology is introduced by Vedung (1998) who makes the distinction between regulative, economic, and informative instruments. These typologies are utilised to place CRFS lab activities on axes that expresses the degree of coerciveness, ranging from voluntary and market-based policy responses to regulative non-voluntary one (Fattibene et al., 2020; Galli et al., 2018; Gelius et al., 2022; Krigsholm et al., 2022; Vedung, 1998). Table 1 presents the typology of policy instruments and interventions in place towards steering the CRFS: regulatory policy instruments, urban planning instruments, economic and market-based instruments, and informational and educational instruments.

Table 1. Policy toolbox for CRFS policies

Instrument category	Examples of policy instruments	Degree of Coerciveness
Regulatory policy instruments	Regulations, standards, rule and requirements, reforms, food safety standards, public procurement principles and criteria, advertisement restrictions	High (‘hard instruments’ and non-voluntary)
Urban planning	Public land acquisition policies, public land allocations, zoning and spatial plans, measures for access to agricultural or vacant lands	
Economic and market-based instruments	Fiscal incentives, tax reductions, financial support, subsidies, nudging tools and brokering	Low (‘soft instruments’ and voluntary)
Informational and educational instruments and programmes	Campaigns and events, raising awareness activities, educational activities, recommendations and food strategies, partnerships and cooperation, advice, and guidelines	

At the moment of authoring this paper, much is unknown about local policy makers’ decision-making processes in food governance (Candel, 2020). Developing CRFS strategies poses choices to local policymakers for tackling multiple food system challenges. Although urban food policies usually emerge from local governments and municipalities, civil society and other urban actors can play a role in the design and introduction of such policies at the city-region level (IPES-Food, 2017). Softer instruments are applied by municipalities as they can be adapted to local contexts, lack implementation costs, and can function as a leverage point for local strategies development, but there might be insufficient when not coupled to hard policy instruments (Kasa et al., 2018). Consequently, a policy mix with various policy interventions can be an effective way forward for city-regions.

Food policy experimentation in CRFS labs

A growing number of city-regions are experimenting with Living Labs, or CRFS labs, as food systems serve multiple functions that are essential to societal welfare, including

public health, individual nutrition, and environmental objectives. CRFS labs aim to activate stakeholders through local experimentation, social innovation, and public involvement, by bringing diverse food actors and stakeholders together to contribute to the transition toward CRFS sustainability. Bulkeley et al. (2016) describe these experimental spaces as *safe zones* that go beyond innovation and extend into urban governance, as they explore methods for setting up urban networks and assess CRFS actors' vision. Policy innovation efforts enable knowledge sharing, empirical testing, and reflection on regulatory reforms. In addition, they may add to the democratisation of CRFS decision making and have an integrative potential in policy formulation in city-region level (Willems et al., 2022).

The CRFS lab approach is inclusive and directly involves stakeholders and urban-rural actors in a collaborative policymaking arena. CRFS labs function within new urban governance forms that fall under the quadruple helix, a framework commonly utilised to examine the development of CRFS labs (Nguyen & Marques, 2022). The model brings science, policy, business, and civil society together, and is widely used to foster innovation and help knowledge and resource-sharing among these parties (Hakeem et al., 2023). This type of approach can reinforce what Giambartolomei et al. (2021) call *policy entrepreneurship*, a collective place-specific leadership of learning-by-doing, and what Moragues-Faus & Morgan (2015) refer to as *food entrepreneurship* and *food champions*. It can also support the development of social innovation, considering citizens as urban stakeholders equal to industrial, market, state, and academic actors.

The Living Lab approach is utilised in various transition studies and debates due to its ability to conceptualise practices; particularly the inclusion of citizens' initiatives into local public policy (Aalbers & Sehested, 2018). Given the challenges in bringing CRFS actors together due to either organisational isolation or competition, Living Labs provide added value because power dynamics between policy actors are known to impact the outcome of policy creation processes (Gamache et al., 2020). Consequently, the Living Lab remains an attractive option for local food system transformation as it may enable integration of the currently fragmented food arena governance and may support more inclusive policy creation processes.

Methodology

This research aims to understand the practical and place-specific dimension of food system thinking and the role of policy experimentation in city-regions. This comparative multiple case study examines EU city-regions that are part of a research consortium into

food system transformation at the city-level; the Cities2030 European Horizon project. Such research method is common in ‘territorial’ and ‘transformation studies’ as it allows for acquiring in-depth, context-specific knowledge, which is crucial for understanding policy processes in a territorial context (Yin, 1994). The research also builds upon the paradigm of reflexive interpretivism as epistemology, focusing on how the groups of actors themselves construct the answers and perceive their own realities. Accordingly, policy experimentation and the CRFS context will be described as perceived by the Labs coordinators themselves.

Data is collected through in-depth semi-structured online interviews with representatives from CRFS labs. The city-regions initiated CRFS labs that focused on innovation and policy elements. The CRFS labs formulate local food agendas and policy action plans including experiments to test interventions on how to transform their CRFS. No selection procedure was used, as all labs were approached for interviews. Prior to the interview, interviewees were requested to sign consent forms to comply with the ethical standards of the researcher institute and the project data collection requirements. The interviews contain three main sections. The first section was dedicated to their perception of sustainability in food systems and city-regions’ approach towards sustainability. The second section addressed the CRFS policy landscape, and examined the various levels of governance levels, ranging from the European to the national, regional, and municipal levels. This entailed the mapping of various power dynamics and relationships among distinct levels of governance and their engagement with local realities. In the third section, insights focused on CRFS labs’ policy efforts and methods of addressing and interpreting CRFS elements. Areas of analysis were adopted from the Cities2030 key thematic areas: production, processing, distribution, markets, consumption, food waste, food security, ecosystem services, livelihoods, and inclusion. These categories are compatible with the MUFPP and Food2030 areas of action (Carey & Cook, 2021) and respond to scholar calls for embedding different dimensions of sustainability of food systems into food governance research (Sonnino et al., 2019).

Lab coordinators were also asked to place their activities and policy efforts onto a *policy matrix*. This matrix consists of a vertical and horizontal axis, with each axis reflecting a policy distinction. The horizontal axis shows the policy instruments (‘Policy Type’), while the vertical axis reflects the governance approach (‘Governance Mode’) indicated by the top-down and bottom-up approaches at its extremes. This distinction is often referred to as the ‘vertical interplay’ in governance (Nilsson et al., 2012). The Matrix allows CRFS labs

to pilot solutions that populate a two-dimensional area and offers a comprehensive visual tool to grasp Labs’ approaches and efforts to CRFS policy experimentation.

Results

Sixteen CRFS labs that were part of the Cities2030 consortium were approached for an interview, which led to thirteen interviews that were held online in October 2022. The labs demonstrate adequate variation in geographical spread (Figure 1) and in organisation types associated with their coordination (Table 2). Interviews were between one and two hours in duration and were each dedicated to one CRFS lab.

Table 2. The city-region food system labs

	City-region	Country	Type of interviewed organisation(s)
1	Murska Sobota	Slovenia	Municipality and NGO
2	Vidzeme	Latvia	Regional public authority and NGO
3	Iasi	Romania	Municipality and university
4	Marseille	France	NGO
5	Veijle	Denmark	Municipality-led organisation
6	Velika Gorica	Croatia	Municipality and SME
7	Quart de Poblet	Spain	Municipality
8	Bremerhaven	Germany	Municipality
9	Bruges	Belgium	University, municipality, and independent external research institute
10	Troodos	Cyprus	University
11	Haarlem	The Netherlands	Municipality
12	Seinäjoki	Finland	Local development company and NGO
13	Vicenza	Italy	Municipality

Figure 1. Location of the CRFS labs included in the study

The interviews provided information on the CRFS characteristics and allowed identification of the policy instruments employed in CRFS. Most labs employ a mix of policy instruments, including non-voluntary and voluntary responses. The instruments that were used most by the CRFS labs consist of informational and educational instruments (e.g., information campaigns, and events), and market-based instruments (e.g., local taxes and economic benefits). All CRFS labs have introduced informational activities to raise awareness about various food system components and territorial challenges. Awareness raising takes place through the policy instruments education, training, information programmes and skills-sharing workshops. Citizens’ participation and engagement is a key priority for such activities. These programmes target various citizen audiences and stimulate conversations that go beyond the established roles of city and citizens and enhance new roles to citizens as co-creators. Sharing responsibilities over urban governance facilitates citizens and stakeholders to contribute not only to the identification of territorial challenges but also to viable solutions and design of food planning.

The tendency of CRFS to move from a top-down to a more bottom-up governance approach is evident in Figure 2. Most policy efforts are concentrated at the bottom-right of the policy matrix, which signifies a tendency towards bottom-up voluntary policy instruments. This is driven by lab coordinators’ attempts to introduce democratic processes in the development of new food projects or strategies and experimenting. A

CRFS lab coordinator describes it: “We wanted to avoid coming up with a food policy which is only the result of an internal debate. For us, the policy lab is not a starting point, but the result of a set of dialogues, activities, knowledge exchange with citizens and experiments”. Stakeholder engagement and co-creation are the main characteristics of a CRFS approach, and this is reflected in the engagement of most CRFS labs partner with local organisations and grassroots organisation to co-design and coordinate CRFS-specific food activities. These stakeholders consist of citizens or community initiatives, NGOs, municipalities from the region and knowledge institutions that share a common vision for transforming their CRFS.

Figure 2. Policy Matrix. Graph is based on lab responses in the current study. Each dot represents a single policy response per Lab, as indicated by the Lab coordinators during the interviews, after receiving a standardised explanation of each axis and their meaning. Responses are also categorised per CRFS thematic area (colours typology). ‘Governance Mode’ on the Y-axis and the ‘Policy Type’ on the X-axis.

Figures two and three present the CRFS focus areas, as indicated by CRFS Lab coordinators. Labs’ interventions commonly address consumption and food waste. Health and sustainable consumption are a widely actionable goal across CRFS labs. Efforts towards a healthy food environment and stimulating the consumption of healthy food and nutrition were addressed concretely by nine labs, while three other labs willing to

prioritise it in future interventions. Lab activities include the development of regional plans and the design of educational programs in collaboration with primary schools, while special consideration is given to stimulating sustainable diets for children through the educational sector in six regions. *“We had this whole action week on the topic of nutrition, with external partners, teachers and NGOs and our motto was ‘eat differently’ presenting good examples of fair and regional community day-care and school catering”* mentions a lab coordinator. Secondly, food waste management is another prominent theme across eight labs, primarily driven by national or regional plans or strategies. CRFS Lab activities address food waste reduction through informative campaigns and workshops aiming at public awareness-building. CRFS labs are often secondary in affecting food waste management yet indicate that food circularity and food waste are becoming a priority area for CRFS actors. Examples of such interventions range from experimental activities such as inviting citizens to daily weight food waste and receiving creative food waste tips, to building restaurant networks to communally tackle food waste.

CRFS elements related to the social dimension of food are poorly addressed by nine labs. As a lab coordinator argues, *“we weren’t used to seeing food as a social matter; we used to tackle its environmental side, but we need to focus more on food security and inclusion in our region”*. Examples of supporting social innovation are present to some city-regions, through citizen-led and grassroots initiatives such as social kitchens and community gardens. Three labs also link food with local culture and heritage.

Figure 3. Policy Matrices showing policy interventions per thematic area. Graph is based on lab responses in the current study. Each dot represents a single policy response per Lab, as indicated by the Lab coordinators during the interviews, after receiving a standardised explanation of each axis and their meaning. ‘Governance Mode’ on the Y-axis and the ‘Policy Type’ on the X-axis.

Labs’ food policy initiatives appear segmented across areas of interest and do not exhibit strong cross-sectoral strategies, which is also evident in Figure 3. Regulative policy instruments have been introduced only in certain CRFS elements (production, distribution and market, livelihoods, and ecosystem services). On the contrary, sustainable consumption is the most targeted element by soft policies, such as events and educational activities. City-regions struggle to introduce concrete food strategies and policies that address their entire CRFS, leading to fragmented interventions of specific food system elements.

The analysis also reveals certain recurring themes across the different governance levels. A theme repeatedly indicated by the CRFS labs is the need to mobilise food system actors at the national level into applying a systemic approach to food system transformation. City-region actors indicate to be isolated in their efforts to introduce a more sustainable urban food agenda, with five lab coordinators sharing experiences of lock-ins or inertia at the national level that constrain activities at the CRFS level. Consequently, CRFS actors skip directives or strategies from the national level and initiate their local policy

experimentations. A lab coordinator mentions they skip the national level, because *“Brussels is perceived to be closer than the national government”*. Simultaneously, city-regions and municipalities at the regional governance level gain new roles, shifting from service providers to agents of change. *“We’re seeing a new role for local government, initiating new projects, and connecting with groups and parties. We are true partners right now and not just the government, you know, signing laws and directives,”* observes a municipality-led lab coordinator.

A recurring theme across multiple interviews and themes is the mandate that CRFS actors have to initiate, alter or implement policies. Five lab coordinators expressed the concern that they have neither mandate, nor power to introduce urban food policies. *“We can influence the CRFS but there is no mandate on doing so”*, states a lab coordinator. Another coordinator explains that [they] *“...don’t have a central responsibility, there’s no department in the administration which is responsible for the CRFS system”*. In contrast to the perceived lack of power and influence of local actors and CRFS labs, national governments are perceived as an essential governance level to deal with CRFS policy elements. Mandate is indicated to be especially relevant to certain CRFS elements such as food waste management.

Finally, CRFS lab interviewees expressed difficulties in achieving cross-scale governance and policy integration. One lab coordinator shares *“...we have achieved this level of knowledge that includes the EU contribution, the national level, and the regional level. What is missing is the capacity to transfer knowledge to local authorities. We still have to work on integrating the three different levels in our work.”* CRFS labs overcome such barriers created by disconnected governance processes by joining city networks and peer groups. CRFS networks serve as enablers for city-to-city exchange of experiential knowledge, awareness, and lobbying. To illustrate, three labs are part of association of regional or provincial municipalities, one lab is member of a national coalition among municipalities with a particular focus on food system sustainability, and one lab is member a global network. Six labs also underline the importance of the MUFPP network. Two labs simultaneously stimulate cross-sector collaboration and integrated governance by establishing food policy networks such as Food Councils. One interviewee shares that [they] *“... work on a higher goal of coordination for our CRFS via a Food Board, bringing together public servants, policymakers, stakeholders, and regional state actors”*.

Discussion

This paper aims to provide insight into the application of Living Labs to sustainably transform urban food systems across city-regions, and to assess the role of policy in this process. Special attention has been devoted to what the literature considers as the most urgent objectives of food system transformation: the achievement of a balance between the social, economic, and environmental dimensions of sustainability, following the FAO definition on food system sustainability (FAO, 2018). City-regions traditionally perceived food to be a domain outside of their policy radar, which has led to a focus on isolated food elements. The adoption of a systems thinking approach stimulates a better understanding of food system complexities, linkages, and feedbacks along components and thereby also support the integration of policy instruments designed to steer the food system towards a social optimum (Ericksen, 2008; Level Panel of Experts on Food Security, 2017). The innovativeness of the CRFS approach is both a lens and tool to re-connect the urban with the rural. Building upon the literature on CRFS and the need for more integrated policies, and due to the delineated territories of city-regions, the CRFS approach can provide systemic solutions oriented to sustainability in food systems and assist in dealing with fragmented knowledge (Blay-Palmer et al., 2018). In practice, Labs try to engage with a broad range of stakeholders including farmers and producers, and actors beyond the physical territorial urban boundaries.

CRFS pilots have developed a wide range of policy initiatives. The majority of policy initiatives are classified as bottom-up and voluntary instruments, yet this typology varies across thematic areas. Voluntary policy types are easier to introduce by pilots compared to the regulatory and urban planning responses. However, CRFS labs also indicated a lack of mandate, which could stimulate the selection of bottom up and mandatory instruments as they fall within the scope of influence of the pilot actors. Such concentration of bottom-up instruments indicates a potential shift from state dominated policies and market-driven forces towards citizen-driven collaborative models where local governments and organisations increasingly claim a role in the development and implementation of new food policies. The role of local governments and cities is evolving from service providers to actors that bring concrete change to local realities, a tendency by cities to connect food with other policy priorities (Sonnino et al., 2019). Resources scarcity and shifting priorities has given space to non-state stakeholders to take responsibility in realising sustainability objectives in the city-region level. Candel's research (2020) also shows that local urban governments act as facilitators for interventions initiated by citizens or local

NGOs. As demonstrated in this research, there are possibilities of institutional entrepreneurship, facilitation and policy experimentation that hold a transformational potential in the urban context (Wolfram et al., 2016).

Living labs are lauded as tools to provide region-specific insights and sites for policy experimentation and urban-rural interventions and CRFS pilots across the EU support this positive sentiment. Place-specific pilots provide new forms of governance where ingrained institutional structures are temporarily lifted, potentially fostering innovative multi-actor collaborations and participating in a shifting governance landscape that shapes urban sustainability transitions (Bulkeley et al., 2016; Willems et al., 2022). Living Labs stimulate participatory and multi-stakeholder governance and have the potential to increase sustainable and just food strategies and safeguard affordable and healthy food for all residents of the CRFS. The engagement of citizens and stakeholders is crucial (Giambartolomei et al., 2021) and local and translocal networks have contributed to the emerging governance models that CRFS labs provide (Moragues-Faus & Sonnino, 2019).

Conclusion

Existing literature on urban food systems and city-region food systems has recognised the role of cities and urban policies as catalysts to face the multiple threats of existing globalised food systems. This multiple case study-research demonstrates that Living Labs can indeed stimulate CRFS transformation through supporting cross-scale governance and policy interventions that address multiple elements of the CRFS. Living Labs achieve this by initiating new forms of collaboration and assigning new roles to traditional food actors. They are proven to be fertile ground to experiment with food system alterations and food policy integration within the region, while adopting a system thinking approach, in a manner that is most fitting to the CRFS characteristics and policy context.

Living Labs demonstrate to be an effective tool in CRFS transformation to be more sustainable and equitable, leading to an increase in social welfare of city-regions. Scholars and urban practitioners use multiple levels of citizen participation to enable citizens' and stakeholders' active involvement; consisting of informative, consultive, participative or involving, collaborative and empowering (Foroughi et al., 2023). This multi-level approach provides city-regions and local governments with opportunities to move towards more inclusive and collaborative governance models while enabling cross-scale governance. The way forward to reach more sustainable and just food systems has been identified as actively questioning the status-quo of top-down food system governance (Moragues-Faus

& Sonnino, 2019) and Living Labs across Europe are working towards finding solutions tailored to their specific CRFS through collective and participatory governance.

This research is highly exploratory due to its experimental nature and the early phase of lab development, yet it reveals the need for a comprehensive analysis of potential outcomes and the role of CRFS in delivering well-round sustainable policies. The diversity of CRFS and the resulting variation across the Living Labs assessed in this study would make the generalisation of study conclusions across CRFS speculative. However, this study uncovered characteristics of and barriers to CRFS transformation that are common across the city-regions included in the sample. These themes require additional research given the urgency and growing interest in urban food governance by scholars, urban-rural practitioners, and policymakers. Future research should aim to provide evidence of the outcomes of CRFS labs' activity after the labs have been fully developed and ex-ante assessment can take place. Interest goes out to providing an understanding of the circumstances under which Living Labs can have long-term impact and efficiently dismantle governance silos to reach societal benefits. The identification of best practices and facilitating an understanding of the role of cities in urban-rural linkages will support the development of efficient policy interventions under the CRFS approach.

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